

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

A real-world data collection framework for a fused dataset creation for joint human and remotely operated vehicle monitoring and anomalous command detection

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Abstract

Unmanned Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROVs) are widely used in safety-critical missions, spanning across monitoring, surveillance, and search and rescue missions. In most cases, the human operator controls the ROV under stressful conditions and in harsh environments. The physical and mental states of the operator are vital as they may cause involuntary movements, issuing unintentional commands due to fatigue or stress. Consequently, a joint monitoring mechanism that will assess the operator's commands can be beneficial in preventing potentially catastrophic events, such as accidents. To this end, in this study, we propose a data collection framework for creating a fused dataset, consisting of data obtained from both the human operator and the ROV, and we integrate stress induction to stimulate stress and fatigue that may affect operators during missions. We optimise the dataset, which includes the operator's physiological signals and inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensor data from the ROV, using data fusion approaches and feature extraction. We evaluate the dataset through the statistical analysis, illustrating a statistical difference between data characterising normal and involuntary commands. Finally, we evaluate the optimised and original datasets over a variety of classifiers, demonstrating an accuracy of 94% and 95%, respectively.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Constant technological advancements in the area of remotely operated (terrestrial and aerial) vehicles (ROVs) facilitate their widespread use in a variety of applications, spanning across various domains. Modern applications of ROVs include search and rescue missions, surveillance, disaster management, etc. In particular, there is a growing attention in search and rescue missions as well as emergency response services, since ROVs can be equipped with an abundance of sensors, and can assist in decision and support in multiple scenarios. However, operating the ROV in harsh environments, such as natural and man-made disasters, and emergency response scenarios induces stress to the operator and also increases fatigue levels. The operator is thus prone to give divergent commands during

the mission or even unable to control the vehicle. Furthermore, accidents may occur as a result of fatigue and increased workload levels, which can be monitored using non-invasive sensors. Additionally, modern ROVs are equipped with inertial sensors that provide control and state estimation of the ROV. Consequently, being able to jointly monitor the state of both human and device concurrently, we can encode contextual awareness in the form of fused sensor data extracted in real time, thus enabling detection of normal and abnormal conditions. By installing a shared control system on the ROV, which can detect the operator's involuntary commands, that is, due to stress, the operator moves his/her finger on the joystick of the remote controller involuntarily, thus instructing the ROV to move towards an unwanted direction. A variety of studies have investigated the design of a mechanism for

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monitoring and controlling ROVs, such as rescue missions with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [1–3]. While many factors can affect a mission, for example, human operator experience, weather conditions, technical issues, etc., and since ROVs do not always provide a mechanism for preventing accidents and ensuring safe operation, the need for such monitoring and control mechanisms is imperative. The human's workload and fatigue levels must be assessed in real time since the operator's mental state can be affected by factors, such as stress, fatigue, operating in harsh environmental conditions, as well as time intervals that demand high concentration and dedication to a specific task. There is a variety of efforts to monitor the mental state of human operators, including questionnaires [4, 5], facial expressions, videos, and body movements [6]; however, the most promising ones rely on biological markers [5, 7, 8]. In particular, there are two approaches for monitoring human workload: vision-based and sensor-based [9], with the former employing cameras to monitor the operator and attempt to record operation workload, while the latter approaches utilise wearable sensors. In this context, sensor-based methods are more suitable for human workload monitoring [9] as biological markers or physiological signals can be monitored using wearable and non-invasive sensors placed on the individual. Physiological signals provide important information about the human mental or physical state that cannot be detected from facial expressions, voice tone, body movements, etc. [9]. Furthermore, there is a plethora of non-invasive sensors that record physiological signals, which can be used in these cases [2, 10].

Similarly, if we consider data only from the human operator during a mission, it will result in a restrictive modelling of the ROV's operational context, potentially failing to capture its state in relevance to each issued command. On the other hand, a joint mechanism for monitoring the operator and the ROV simultaneously encapsulates a holistic contextual awareness and through machine learning can be trained to perform anomaly detection. Additionally, as we assume that this shared control mechanism will be deployed on the ROV, it optimises and significantly reduces the amount of data that should be processed in order to provide real-time decision support with low power requirements. Such a joint monitoring mechanism needs to monitor both the human and the ROV using minimal amount of data, which will then be fed into a machine learning (ML)-based classifier (anomaly detector) that will be deployed on a resource-constrained device, with low energy consumption and processing time and at the same time is expected to provide high classification accuracy. Similar anomaly detection approaches use simulators to create data for evaluating the developed ML methodologies. In contrast, in this work, we aim to collect real-world data, which is one of the main contributions of the present study. To the best of our knowledge, there is no real-world dataset consisting of fused data capturing both the mental and physical states of human operators and the operational context of an ROV during a mission. In this study, we present a framework for the creation of a dataset consisting of data from both the human operator and the ROV. In detail, the contributions of this manuscript significantly extend our initial work in [11]:

- We include Heart Rate (HR) monitoring in conjunction with surface Electromyography (sEMG).
- We also evaluate more features, including the HR, which were not included in our initial approach.
- We additionally integrate a stress induction technique for stimulating stress and fatigue similar to real-life search and rescue missions.
- We expand the mission course and mission objectives by incorporating an additional mission task.
- We also compare two feature selection schemes, providing a detailed trade-off analysis for each scheme.
- Overall, this manuscript features a comprehensive description of the data collection procedures and protocols as well as an extended discussion on trade-offs between each feature selection scheme and results associated with the importance of each feature in terms of overall performance of the joint monitoring framework.

In particular, the contributions of this work are the following:

- A data collection framework is used for creating a real-world dataset that fuses data from human operators and ROVs during missions in varying conditions.
- The dataset consists of physiological signals (sEMG signal and HR) acquired non-invasively from operators with different degrees of experience as well as the ROV's inertial sensors (jointly recorded).
- We integrate a stress induction technique to stimulate and capture involuntary movements under stress, attempting to reproduce the conditions during a mission.
- We optimise the dataset with data fusion and feature extraction to minimise dimensionality for real-time classification with low computational overheads.
- We perform the statistical analysis showing the statistical difference between normal and abnormal movements.
- We evaluate through various classifiers the accuracy of the optimised and full datasets, showing negligible accuracy reduction when using the optimised dataset.

The rest of the paper provides an overview of existing similar approaches in Section 2. The proposed data collection framework and our methodology towards the optimised dataset are described in Section 3. Section 4 presents the results evaluating the dataset and the effectiveness of the data collection framework. Finally, conclusions and future work are discussed in Section 5.

2 | BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

There are several works focussing on human or ROV monitoring with few studies addressing joint monitoring of humans and ROV, which are presented in the following section. The majority of studies focus on detecting anomalies in the operator's mental and physical states using wearable sensors and

audio-visual monitoring techniques, which are widely proposed for driver assistance units, critical infrastructure operators, etc. Furthermore, studies addressing stress monitoring are discussed, employing only non-invasive techniques. Since, few studies exist focussing on the human operator for ROVs (in particular, on UAV pilots), we discuss these works as well as studies on joint ROV and human operator monitoring.

2.1 | Human monitoring

Various studies address how to monitor the mental or physical state of humans during various tasks [1, 4, 12]. The mental state of a person can be evaluated using questionnaires and physiological signals that represent fatigue due to the performed task [8, 13]. Moreover, monitoring the movements of different body parts, according to the mission, may be beneficial for detecting stress and fatigue. In our previous work [11], we suggested that the sEMG from the operator's right hand, in addition to the IMU sensor data from the UAV, can be fused to construct a small, yet an effective dataset that can be classified by a classifier executed on a low-power processor [11]. Furthermore, since HR yields promising results in detecting stress and fatigue during a mission, it was also included in the proposed approach.

Monitoring the sEMG signal from the operator's hands has also received significant scientific attention over the past decade [7, 13]. Such studies use an armband or electrodes placed on the person's forearm to monitor the gestures [14, 15]. In an effort to effectively classify hand gestures using the sEMG signal, authors in [7] propose a variety of features and classification techniques with time- and frequency-domain features evaluated in 3 different datasets. High and low sampling rates were compared in [15] and features with lower sampling rates were proposed, which are also extracted in our approach, since the device we selected is categorised into low sampling rate devices. A support vector machine (SVM) classifier was employed for the classification of movements. Another approach for hand gesture recognition is described in [14], where authors use sEMG signals within the human-machine interaction (HMI) interface. A MYO armband was used and features extracted from sEMG signal were proposed, achieving the highest performance in conjunction with an artificial neural network (ANN) for classification.

HR has also been used to detect stress levels, which exhibited correlation on subjects' stress state, regarding short-term mental stress. It has been also used as a feature in a variety of studies addressing stress detection in humans [13, 16]. In [16], a new design of a wearable embedded system for online cognitive workload monitoring is proposed. Multiple signals are monitored (respiration (RSP), HR, skin temperature (ST) and pulse waveform) as a part of a multi-channel physiological signal acquisition and a low power processing platform. The proposed wearable system can continuously monitor multiple bio-signals and provide reliable detection of high and other cognitive workload levels. Additionally, in [13], stress detection is achieved through the monitoring of EMG and electrocardiography (ECG) signals during various tasks under time pressure and in stressful environment. A questionnaire was used to assess stress levels and different features

were extracted for EMG and ECG signals, the results demonstrating the effectiveness of EMG signal for multi-level stress detection. Another approach is described in [17], where authors monitored 13 drone pilots by recording the HR, ST, RSP and skin conductance (SC) signals. Neuro-fuzzy models were trained to recognise the altered states of the pilot. The model was trained with the operator's signal under normal circumstances with no anxiety and with stress, identifying changes in operators' mental and/or physical states. In this approach, authors monitored the emotional state of the drone operator in order to recognise situations that cannot be controlled during the flight. Moreover, in [18], HR and inter-beat-interval (IBI) were monitored during two flying tasks from 32 pilots, suggesting that HR is a good indicator of stress or fatigue levels. Therefore, in the present study, we include HR as one of the monitoring signals. Next, we provide some background on sEMG and HR to familiarise readers on how these signals are used.

2.1.1 | Surface electromyography (sEMG)

sEMG is a non-invasive technique for measuring human muscle activity during muscular contractions [7, 15]. Recording the bio-electric potentials that occur from muscular contraction can be very useful in clinical and research studies. To this end, bipolar surface electrodes are placed on the person's muscles to record the EMG signal, which can be used for recognising bodily movements, including hand gestures. Furthermore, dedicated equipment is employed for recording myoelectric signals and is a key factor for movement and hand gesture recognition. The recommended frequency range for acquiring sEMG signals is between 5 and 500 Hz [7]. Moreover, there are two types of devices for monitoring the EMG signal: insertion and surface sensors. The former method is an invasive approach for collecting EMG signal and includes the insertion sensors, while surface electrodes are considered non-invasive [19]. However, while the insertion sensors are more accurate, in this study, we employed surface electrodes as we want a non-invasive approach to monitor the human operator. Additionally, two categories of surface electrodes exist: passive and active. Three conductors are included in active (differential) electrodes [19] with one of the three being located close to analysed muscle for detecting the muscular activity. The other two conductors are located before and after the first one, along the same muscle. On the other hand, passive electrodes consist of one conductor only and a conductive material is required to guarantee an optimal coupling with the skin [19]. The sEMG signal has been used in a variety of studies proposing detection and classification of stress and fatigue of muscles [7, 13, 15]. In our study, we chose the non-invasive technique for recording sEMG signals to monitor muscular contraction.

2.1.2 | Heart rate (HR)

HR is the speed of the heartbeat divided by the number of heartbeats per unit of time [9]. At rest (known as resting HR), the

average adult's heartbeats vary between 60 and 100 beats per minute (BPM). A critical situation alters the physiological signals of human as stated in [9, 17, 18], and this is reflected in HR, IBI, temperature and RSP. Even emotions can significantly impact the HR, while an increased HR has been also associated with increased levels of mental workload [18]. Moreover, physical and cognitive workload can lead to increased HR [9] and changes in stress can be detected in HR [10].

2.1.3 | Other physiological signals

Additional signals that have been used to monitor stress and mental state of humans include electrodermal activity (EDA), which is also known as galvanic skin response (GSR) or SC, blood volume pulse (BVP), photoplethysmography (PPG) and ST. EDA is the measurement of electricity through the skin of the subject and it has been shown to be a good indicator of stress in humans [10]. This signal was used in many studies due to the fact that increased stress results in increased EDA since the skin gets sweat [10]. Furthermore, blood volume is the amount of blood in tissue during a specific time interval. BVP measurement is the amount of light that is reflected by the surface of the skin [10]. These light reflections occur from the flow of the blood through the vessels after each heartbeat. BVP can be measured by a PPG sensor, which measures the reflected light through the skin. When stress increases, the measurement of BVP is lower and vice versa [10]. Additionally, ST is the temperature measured from hand's surface and it can be combined with other physiological signals and measurements in order to classify stress levels and fatigue of human. As stated in [10], increasing temperature values relate to decreasing stress levels.

2.2 | ROV sensor data

ROVs, and specifically UAVs, are equipped with several sensors that monitor the state of the ROV, the state of the

environment, and also provide assistance and guidance to the ROV and the operator during a mission [2]. Typically, the on-board ROV controller and the operator make use of these signals as feedback, facilitating autonomous control (for the ROV) and assisting the operator in perceiving in real time, the status of the ROV, its location, direction of motion, velocity, etc. In our approach, we aim to utilise data from these sensors, fused with the human operator's physiological data, and build a real-time ML-based classifier that will be located on board the ROV; thus, we aim for a resource-constrained classification of these signals. This leads to several constraints, such as low memory footprint, low processing time, and low energy consumption. Similar studies in the literature aim to use on-board sensing data to provide assistance to the ROV during a mission; for instance, a light-weight, low-power, built-in controller is described in [3], which aims to monitor and predict a dangerous scenario of multirotor UAVs. An ANN is used to recognise a dangerous scenario right before it happens without being trained under specific dangerous conditions. In [3], the gyroscope and accelerometer sensors are employed, along with data from the IMU of the UAV, such as compass and barometer, with promising results. There are several different approaches for multi-rotor UAV controllers, including model predictive control (MPC), fuzzy, neurofuzzy and Lyapunov-based control [20]. Moreover, control using neural networks, data-driven, proportional-integral-derivative (PID), hybrid and adaptive control are also proposed. We also used data from accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer and barometer sensors for our approach since most commercial ROVs are equipped with such sensors, aiming to capture the state of the ROV with the least amount of data. In Table 1, we present a brief description of these sensors. As mentioned in [3], data provided by these sensors are related to motion, velocity, altitude and direction of motion. Furthermore, these sensors do not rely on any external communication and do not require any further information to declare the ROV state. This makes an ideal choice for estimating the ROV state during a mission where external communication may not be available.

TABLE 1 Description of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) sensors.

Sensor	Description
Accelerometer	Measures the acceleration in the 3 axes, which plays an important role for measuring velocity of the drone.
Gyroscope	Records the rotational motion of the UAV over the 3 axes [3]. By measuring the rotational movement of the drone, losing balance and control is prevented.
Magnetometer	Detects the changes in drone's orientation and gives feedback to the UAV for returning back to its intended direction [3].
Barometer:	
a. Altitude	Measures the altitude through atmospheric pressure. Data given by the altitude sensor are useful for detecting if the operator gives a sudden command to change the UAV's altitude. We can also identify changes in altitude due to weather conditions, such as wind bursts.
b. Relative height	Gives a similar measurement to the altitude reading, which is the difference in height from the take-off point.

2.3 | Joint human and ROV monitoring

Relevant works targeting joint human and ROV monitoring focus on aviation and automotive industry applications [1, 12, 21]. For example, during a rescue mission using drones on a simulator, ECG, PPG, RSP and ST were collected from the human operator in [1], and a plethora of features were calculated, identifying the 26 most informative. In the present study, we followed the analysis of [1] and used some of the proposed features, also employing various classifiers, such as k-nearest neighbour (KNN), decision tree (DT), Gaussian naive bayes (GNB), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), SVM, X-gradient boosting (XGB) and logistic regression (LR).

However, the rest of the works focus only on using the ROV as part of collecting data and monitoring human operators without utilising the ROV's data at all. For example, an approach for assistance in rescue missions was proposed in [2], where the operator was monitored via the ECG signal. In addition, features in time and frequency domains were extracted and used for classification. In [2], the authors proposed a newly designed simulator for inducing different levels of cognitive workload related to rescue missions with UAVs. In another study [12], the authors proposed advancements, whereby additional physiological signals for human monitoring were used, such as PPG, ST, EDA, ECG and Impedance Cardiogram. A feature selection technique and a feature elimination approach were employed to select the best features. In another related work, a system for the detection of driving stress was designed [21], and authors recorded the ECG, GSR and RSP from 9 participants in real environments. Features were extracted and classified using a mixture of classifiers that were able to distinguish between different stress levels across various sections of driving. Another comprehensive and generalisable internet of things (IoT)-based stress-level detection method is proposed in [22]. The monitored physiological signals were EDA, EMG, RSP and HR. Pre-processing included normalisation of the signals prior and after feature extraction with different features extracted from each signal. The dataset consisted of data taken, while the subjects were driving on a prescribed route including city streets and highways. Thus, the proposed

methods for assessing the stress level demonstrated promising results when evaluated on a real-life dataset. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are limited efforts that combine data from both the ROV and the operator attempting to concurrently decrease energy consumption and processing time [2]. We strongly believe that such framework would greatly benefit both operators and missions in general, preventing undesirable events, such as accidents. Our objective is to develop such a mechanism by jointly and concurrently monitoring the physiological signals of the operator and the ROV. We also propose a data collection framework to generate a real-world dataset under realistic conditions both for human, that is, stress induction, and by developing realistic ROV missions using a commercially available UAV.

3 | PROPOSED DATASET COLLECTION FRAMEWORK

The dataset consists of data from a human operator and a UAV as an ROV during a mission. The whole process and all devices used to evaluate the proposed framework are presented in Figure 1. In the following paragraphs, we present in detail the setup for data acquisition and processing of the signals. Additionally, we describe the stress induction technique that was incorporated as well as assessment of stress. Finally, data fusion and feature extraction are performed with the latter to including two feature selection schemes.

Plenty of challenges had to be overcome prior to the design of the proposed framework related to experimental setup, data collection and processing. As mentioned above, few studies exist for joint monitoring of human and ROV in which data were collected through simulation environment. Concerning experimental setup, the sensors for monitoring physiological signals had to be defined, focussing on non-invasive approaches, in order not to create discomfort to the operator allowing the control of the ROV to be performed as in usual scenarios. Regarding the ROV and as described in Section 2.2, we preferred a device employed with all mentioned sensors to avoid the use of additional ones, potentially inducing further

FIGURE 1 Dataset collection setup.

FIGURE 2 Proposed procedure to acquire the joint dataset for monitoring and control.

communication overheads between the ROV and the added sensing devices.

With regard to data collection procedure, synchronization of sensing devices used for signal acquisition and video recording had to be accomplished by the coordinator as shown in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows the procedure followed for the data acquisition. On the other hand, safety personnel ensured safety of both the participants and the ROV and assisted in video recording of the operator's hand during the mission. Following data collection, labelling and data manipulation took place to match the timestamps of the collected signals and videos.

3.1 | Dataset acquisition setup and processing

We used a remotely piloted drone as an ROV for the construction of the proposed dataset. Operators with different degrees of experience were included in the study, that is, subjects that have not operated an ROV before, subjects with a few flight hours and subjects that operate an ROV every day. By including operators with different levels of experience, we can stimulate and capture the unintentional or involuntary movements given by the operator during a stressful mission. These movements and changes can be similar to those of an experienced operator during a critical mission under pressure and fatigue. During the first trial of evaluating the proposed acquisition framework, we included male and female operators from 20 to 40 years old. Data from 6 healthy subjects were collected with each operator instructed to perform a pre-defined course of movements.

To monitor hand movements of the operator during the mission, one sEMG sensor was used, since we preferred to monitor the on-air motion of the ROV only, for evaluating the proposed framework. We acquired data from the right hand only as shown in Figure 6, despite the fact that not all subjects were right-handed, since we focussed on horizontal ROV movements controlled by the joystick on the right, that is, right, left, forward, and backward. The left hand, controlling the joystick on the left, yields changes in ROV's height and rotation. Each subject is instructed to hold a movement for 3–5 s with a resting period of 10 s between movements to avoid fatigue. The instructed movements were repeated 2 times and the flight duration varied between 10 and 12 min. The repetition of the instructed

FIGURE 3 Drone captures during data collection.

FIGURE 4 Human and Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) sensing devices. (a) MYO Armband, (b) Polar OH1 Heart Rate (HR) Sensor, and (c) DJI Spark Drone.

movements aims to stimulate the fatigue that occurs under stressful conditions and after long periods of controlling the drone. Additionally, we added an additional path to be followed by the subjects to induce stress during the flight. After completing the 2 repetitions with the movements mentioned above, participants had to navigate the drone around a sign as shown in Figure 3. This was an additional path that the subjects had to follow to increase the difficulty of the experiment, especially for the non-experienced pilots.

Moreover, operators were asked to fill in a questionnaire at the beginning and at the end of the experiment to assess stress levels. All the devices used for the purpose of this research work are presented in Figure 4 and described in the following paragraphs, including sampling frequencies, data transmission, connectivity, etc. It is worth mentioning that any commercial HR and sEMG sensors can be used in data collection. Finally, a record of raw data consists of 20 signals consisting, 8 values

from the sEMG signal, 1 value for HR and 11 values from the ROV's IMU.

3.1.1 | Human signal acquisition

The MYO armband (Figure 4a) was used for the acquisition of the sEMG signal, which employs eight EMG active electrodes [23]. MYO is used for recording sEMG data from a person's forearm and its sampling rate is set by default at 200 Hz, while transmission of sEMG data is achieved via a Bluetooth connection to any host computer.

We used the Polar OH1 HR sensor, shown in Figure 4b for HR acquisition, which is an optical HR sensor. It can be used as a standalone device or along with any applications having Bluetooth and ANT+connectivity. In our case, the transmission of data is achieved via a Bluetooth connection. By using the Polar Beat application provided by Polar, HR monitoring can begin at session initiation and end at session completion, where the recording is uploaded to the cloud. The sampling frequency of Polar OH1 HR sensor is 1 Hz.

3.1.2 | ROV signal acquisition

The DJI Spark (Figure 4c) was used as an ROV [24]. The DJI Spark allows to record data, for example, drone's IMU, for each flight, which can be accessed after the flight by using DJI Assistant Software. The data used in this study were from the accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer and barometer, which provide the altitude and relative height measurements. We utilise these sensors since most of the commercial devices are employed with these types of sensors; hence, we eliminated the need of external sensors or devices. We utilise altitude and relative height given from the barometer, additionally to the data used in our previous approach [11]. A description of the sensors of a UAV is provided in Table 1. The sampling rate of DJI Spark is 200 Hz. It is worth mentioning that an experienced pilot was present during the experiment in order to ensure the safety of the operators and the ROV.

3.1.3 | Stress induction

To induce stress to the operators, we adopted two acquisition setups: (a) the operators were instructed to follow the described course and (b) we incorporated a stress induction technique by exposing the subjects to random irritating sounds via headphones during the second part of the experiment. The dataset of sounds used is described in [25]. The same experiment was conducted two times in order to collect more data (a set of data without stress and a set of data with stress induction). In total, 112732 records of data were collected. The dataset without stress induction consists of 57,371 records of data with an average of 9561 from each subject. The dataset with stress induction consists of 55,361 records of data with an average of 9226 from each subject.

3.1.4 | Stress assessment

Stress assessment was achieved by using the state-trait anxiety inventory (STAI) evaluation questionnaire [26, 27]. The subject has to fill in the same questionnaire at the beginning and at the end of the experiment. The evaluation aims to extract two values for the anxiety. First, the state anxiety, which is the stress that occurs from a situation in a specific time and it can vary from day to day. Second, the trait anxiety, which is the stress that occurs from permanent situations in subject's everyday life [26]. The questionnaire consists of 40 questions and the subject needs approximately 10 min to complete it. The first 20 questions are used to extract the state anxiety value or STAI Y-1, while the remaining 20 questions are used for the trait anxiety value or STAI Y-2. As stated in [26], the average values for STAI Y-1 and STAI Y-2 are 43 and 42, respectively. Most of the times, as stated in [26], the values extracted from this method range from 20 to 80.

In our approach, the subjects were asked to fill in the questionnaire prior to data collection and at the end of the experiment. In Table 2, we present the values for state (STAI Y-1) and trait anxiety (STAI Y-2) before and after data collection. As can be seen in Table 2, the value of STAI Y-1 is higher after the experiment compared to the value before the data collection, while the value of STAI Y-2 is slightly lower after the data collection. Moreover, the value of STAI Y-2 is higher than the value of STAI Y-1 prior and after the data collection. Importantly, values of STAI Y-2 are almost equal suggesting that irrespective of whether the participants exhibit anxiety as part of their personality, findings from STAI Y-1 clearly show that they have experienced more stress after the experiment.

3.1.5 | Data fusion

Following data collection from the sEMG sensor, the HR sensor and the ROV, we combine all the data as shown in Figure 5. By using the timestamp of all the collected signals, a single data stream was created. As stated in section 3.1, we acquired 8 sEMG signals, 1 HR value and 11 values from the ROV. In total, each record of data consists of 20 values. The 11 values from the ROV's IMU correspond to the accelerometer (x, y, z), gyroscope (x, y, z), magnetometer (x, y, z), altitude and relative height. After data fusion, we annotated manually all the data, as voluntary or involuntary movements, based on the way each movement was performed. For labelling the collected data, we used two cameras during data collection: one was used for recording the operator's hands (Figures 6 and 7) and the

TABLE 2 Stress assessment (state-trait anxiety inventory (STAI) evaluation).

	Before	After
STAI Y-1	31.5	39
STAI Y-2	39.5	39.33
Total	71	73

FIGURE 5 Dataset generation diagram: combination of the data collected with stress and without stress induction, followed by extraction of the described features and classification using either raw data or the extracted features. With blue colour, we indicate the raw fused data of human and Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV), while with green, we present the features from both the human and the ROV.

FIGURE 6 Experimental setup for data collection.

FIGURE 7 Hand captures during data collection.

other for capturing the panoramic view of each flight, which includes the drone and the operator (Figures 6 and 3). Through the analysis of acquired videos, all time frames associated with unstable or unintentional movements from the operator were annotated as abnormal.

Moreover, we utilise feature extraction in order to decrease the data given as input to the classifier, ultimately achieving real-time monitoring and control of the ROV using an on-board embedded device. In the following section, we present the steps towards dimensionality reduction, assuming that it will have an impact in memory footprint, processing time and energy consumption. In this study, the main goal is to maintain high performance in classification accuracy with the remainders evaluated in future studies. In the following paragraphs, we describe the features extracted from the sEMG and ROV data, followed by the feature selection schemes.

3.2 | Feature extraction

Feature extraction is an important step before classification and in the present study, we evaluated 11 time-domain features from the sEMG signal as follows: variance (VAR), waveform length (WL), mean absolute value (MAV), root mean square (RMS), minimum (MIN), maximum (MAX), integrated absolute value (IAV), simple square integral (SSI), zero crossings (ZC), slope sign change (SSC) and Willison amplitude (WAMP). The description of each signal is presented in Table 3. No features were extracted from the HR value, while from the ROV's data, the Median, Mean, Maximum (Max) and Minimum (Min) values were calculated. We also examine two different feature selection schemes, that is, statistical analysis and feature importance score, which are described in the following paragraphs.

3.2.1 | Statistical analysis (feature selection scheme 1)

To select features through statistical analysis, a paired t -test was performed to examine whether the two classes of

TABLE 3 Description of features extracted from the surface Electromyography (sEMG) signal.

Feature	Description
VAR	Uses the power of the sEMG signal as a feature [28].
WL	Measures the signal complexity in a set of values [28].
MAV	Detection of muscle contraction levels [28].
RMS	Relates to the constant force and non-fatiguing contraction [28].
IAV	Onset index to detect the muscle activity [28].
MAX	-
MIN	-
SSI	Represents the energy of the sEMG signal [28].
ZC	An approximate estimation of frequency-domain properties of the signal. It is defined as the number of times that the amplitude value of sEMG signal crosses the y-axis [28].
SSC	Another method for extracting frequency-domain information of the sEMG signal. Number of changes between positive and negative slopes among three consecutive segments [28].
WAMP	Relates to the firing of motor unit action potential (MUAP) and the muscle contraction level [28].

Abbreviations: IAV, integrated absolute value; MAV, mean absolute value; MAX, maximum; MIN, minimum; RMS, root mean square; SSC, slope sign change; SSI, simple square integral; VAR, variance; WAMP, Willison amplitude; WL, waveform length; ZC, zero crossings.

movements differ significantly as shown in Tables 4–7 and Figures 8 and 9. With regard to signal features from human, the VAR, WL, MAX, MIN, SSI, and IAV were selected (shown in bold in Tables 4, 6 and Figure 8), where it can be seen that the statistical significance was observed in all of the extracted features and the HR as well, which is used as a raw value. As far as ROV signal-related features is concerned, the Min and Mean were selected (Tables 5, 7 and Figure 9).

1. Average values

In order to identify the most suitable features for the design of a shared-control mechanism to jointly monitor the human and the ROV during a mission, the average values were extracted and are shown in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. As can be observed, features with a large difference in their average values were selected for the classification. These features are: VAR, WL, MAX, MIN, SSI and IAV, also marked with bold in Table 4, while MAV and RMS demonstrated smaller differences. The remaining features exhibited marginal differences and are deemed not as important as those mentioned above, while HR exhibited a significant difference between normal and abnormal movements. Regarding the ROV data, Mean and Min were the features with the highest difference compared to the Median and Max. In both human and ROV, the average values of raw data were almost identical between normal and abnormal movements.

TABLE 4 Average values from human data.

Raw	Features		Normal	Abnormal	
	Normal	Abnormal			
S1	-0.8841	-0.8887	VAR	60.8515	26.2588
S2	-0.9635	-0.9766	WL	45.1968	29.1981
S3	-0.9765	-1.0078	MAV	4.5643	2.8405
S4	-0.9440	-0.9476	ZC	0.8013	0.4725
S5	-1.0326	-1.0207	WAMP	0.7037	0.2277
S6	-0.9628	-0.9266	RMS	7.7020	5.2827
S7	-0.8996	-0.8913	SSC	0.5904	0.2225
S8	-0.8930	-0.8875	MAX	9.1102	6.1087
			MIN	-10.9642	-7.521
HR	88.4088	73.3498	SSI	635.92	270.272
			IAV	39.7743	27.7568

TABLE 5 Average values from ROV data.

Raw	Features		Normal	Abnormal	
	Normal	Abnormal			
AccX	0.0029	0.0386	Median	0.5828	0.7845
AccY	0.0049	0.0146	Max	926.743	933.006
AccZ	-1.0193	-1.0204	Min	-615.310	-648.289
GyroX	0.3797	-0.0072	Mean	71.178	65.9762
GyroY	0.0301	-0.1444			
GyroZ	0.3712	-0.0297			
MagX	382.961	356.363			
MagY	-606.773	-647.805			
MagZ	921.159	930.013			
Altitude	81.5456	83.9176			
Rel. Height	4.4308	4.9170			

2. Statistical t -test

Following the estimation of average values, a statistical t -test was performed between normal and abnormal movements (Tables 6 and 7) to identify differences, that is, the obtained p -value is less than 0.05, suggesting that the data from the two classes were significantly different. The t -test analysis between the raw data from the human led in not rejecting the null hypothesis, which in turn signifies that is challenging to achieve a high classification accuracy if we use the raw data. With regard to data from the ROV, the majority of measured variables exhibited the statistical significance for both raw and features (p -value < 0.05).

TABLE 6 *t*-test for human data.

Raw	Features		Raw	Features	
	<i>p</i> -value	(<i>p</i> < 0.05)		<i>p</i> -value	(<i>p</i> < 0.05)
					√
S1	0.8618	×	VAR	**	√
S2	0.7667	×	WL	**	√
S3	0.6024	×	MAV	**	√
S4	0.9443	×	ZC	**	√
S5	0.7845	×	WAMP	**	√
S6	0.4404	×	RMS	**	√
S7	0.8725	×	SSC	**	√
S8	0.9108	×	MAX	**	√
			MIN	**	√
HR	0	√	SSI	**	√
			IAV	**	√

Notes: Values denoted with ** are $<10^{-8}$.

TABLE 7 *t*-test for Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) data.

Raw	Features		Raw	Features	
	<i>p</i> -value	(<i>p</i> < 0.05)		<i>p</i> -value	(<i>p</i> < 0.05)
AccX	0	√	Median	0.0005	√
AccY	**	√	Max	0.3161	×
AccZ	0.1826	×	Min	**	√
GyroX	0.0120	√	Mean	0.0001	√
GyroY	0.1474	×			
GyroZ	**	√			
MagX	**	√			
MagY	**	√			
MagZ	**	√			
Altitude	0	√			
Rel. Height	**	√			

Notes: Values denoted with ** are $<10^{-8}$.

3. Graphical representation of the dataset

We extracted boxplots of features between normal and abnormal movements for visual comparison as well (Figures 8 and 9). The features that showed the significant difference of the human data (Figure 8) are the VAR, WL, MAX, MIN, SSI and IAV. HR has shown a significant difference as well. On the other hand, ZC, WAMP and SSC features did not exhibit any differences, suggesting that their use would not improve classification performance. Moreover, there is a slight difference between MAV and RMS features of sEMG signals. The boxplots for features extracted from the data of the ROV are shown in Figure 9 with Mean and Min exhibiting significant

differences, while Median and Max showed smaller differences compared to Mean and Min.

Following the above analysis, that is, extracted average values and the results from the statistical *t*-test, the selected features, consisting the first feature selection scheme for classification, are the VAR, WL, MAX, MIN, SSI, IAV, and HR from the human signals and the Min and Mean, from the ROV data.

3.2.2 | Feature importance score (feature selection scheme 2)

To calculate the feature selection score of each extracted feature, a variety of classifiers were employed: LDA, DT, LR, adaptive boosting (ADA), gradient boosting (GB), random forests (RF), and Extra-Tree (ExTree), which are implemented in Python sklearn library [29]. Following the estimation of feature importance score of the 16 above-mentioned features, these were sorted in descending order and the top 9 features were selected. As in the statistical analysis approach, we choose 9 features (7 from the human and 2 from the ROV data) to facilitate comparison. In an effort to use same 9 features for each classifier, we extracted feature importance scores and then we selected 9 features with the highest performance, ultimately selecting a different combination of features for each classifier.

4 | FRAMEWORK EVALUATION

In this section, we present the results to evaluate the proposed framework. Initially, we discuss findings of analysis between the raw data and all extracted features, followed by the presentation and comparison of the two feature selection schemes. The first feature selection scheme is based on the statistical analysis, while the second is based on the feature importance score.

4.1 | Classification accuracy: Raw data versus features

Classifying the movements of the operator in combination with the data from the ROV is an important step towards the shared-control mechanism that we aim to design in the future. A variety of classifiers were employed in the literature for stress classification and are also used in this study. These classifiers are LDA, SVM, KNN, GNB, DT, LR, quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA), ADA, GB and RF. In Figure 10, we present the results with the dataset divided into 75% for training and 25% for testing without cross-validation (75%–25%), 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validation for raw data and extracted features. Interestingly, the classification of optimised dataset (extracted features) exhibits a small decline in terms of accuracy, when compared to the classification of raw data and will be investigated in the

FIGURE 8 Boxplots of surface Electromyography (sEMG) features (variance (VAR), waveform length (WL), mean absolute value (MAV), zero crossings (ZC), Willison amplitude (WAMP), root mean square (RMS), slope sign change (SSC), maximum (MAX), minimum (MIN), simple square integral (SSI), integrated absolute value (IAV)) and Heart Rate (HR) between Normal (N) and Abnormal (A) movements.

FIGURE 9 Boxplots of Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV) features (Median, Mean, Max, Min) between Normal (N) and Abnormal (A) movements.

FIGURE 10 Classification accuracy (%), over a variety of classifiers, with 75% of the dataset used for training and 25% for testing and different cross-validation schemes (R – Raw data, F – Features).

future if this drop is acceptable and its impact on processing time and energy consumption. On the other hand, by employing the raw data, the DT, ADA and GB classifiers exhibited the highest accuracy (99.9%) compared to the remaining classifiers with 75%–25%, 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validation schemes. The RF classifier yielded 100% accuracy with 75%–25% and an accuracy of 94% with 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validation. However, when features

are used for the classification, DT and GB classifiers exhibit the best performance with approximately 94% accuracy, while ADA yielded 92% accuracy. In general, a drop around 5% is observed when the optimized dataset is set as an input to the classifiers compared to the raw data. As mentioned above, we will examine in the future the impact of this drop in accuracy in processing time, memory footprint and energy consumption. In our previous work [11],

we also observed a drop around 10%, having a significant impact on processing time and energy consumption. Specifically, an average of 10-fold reduction in energy consumption was achieved, rendering the 10% drop in accuracy acceptable, paving the way to achieve real-time low-power classification. Additionally, inferior performance is observed when using the raw data with the QDA (88%) and GNB (86%) classifiers, while GNB classifier shows the lowest accuracy (73%) when classifying the optimised dataset. Finally, SVM exhibited low accuracy with the optimised dataset, that is, 77% and 79% for 5-fold and 10-fold, respectively, while for the case of 75%–25%, an accuracy of 76% was obtained.

4.2 | Classification accuracy: Feature selection schemes

Classification results when applying feature selection schemes are shown in Table 8. Additionally, to 75%–25%, 5-fold and 10-fold, we also performed leave-one-out (LOO) cross-validation. Regarding the 75%–25% cross-validation, the RF and DT classifiers exhibited the highest accuracy of 94%, while GB classifier yielded 93%. For 5-fold and 10-fold cross-validations, the best performance was obtained with DT and GB classifiers with 93% accuracy. Finally, with the LOO cross-validation, LDA exhibited the highest accuracy (70%) followed by QDA and ADA classifiers with an accuracy 69%. The lowest performance was obtained with the SVM classifier in all cases for the first scheme of feature selection.

Concerning feature selection scheme 2, a slightly higher accuracy was achieved (96%) with RF and 94% with GB and DT classifiers in the case of 75%–25% cross-validation

approaches. Additionally, same accuracy levels (94%) were achieved in 5-fold and 10-fold with DT and GB classifiers, while with the LOO cross-validation, 72% and 69% accuracy were obtained with LDA and DT, respectively. Similarly, the lowest performance was obtained by using LR in all cases of cross-validation (75%–25%, 5-fold, 10-fold and LOO). These results suggest that while both feature selection schemes provide similar performance levels, they should be also evaluated in terms of processing time and energy consumption to identify the best trade-off between accuracy, processing time and energy consumption.

5 | CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study presented a real-world dataset collection and construction framework, fusing data collected through monitoring human operator and the ROV during missions. The overall direction is to develop an anomaly detection mechanism that jointly monitors humans and ROVs and detects involuntary commands. The present study addresses data collection, stress induction, data fusion and data annotation. Moreover, data analysis and feature extraction are used to optimise the dataset in an effort to reduce computational complexity, memory and energy footprints of the classifier. The statistical analysis was also performed, extracting the average values from the raw data and the extracted features, enabling the selection of the most suitable features for achieving high accuracy while meeting performance requirements. Statistical analysis results also suggest significant differences between the two classes of movements (normal/abnormal) both for the optimised and the full dataset. Moreover, two schemes for feature selection were compared to also determine the most suitable features.

TABLE 8 Classification accuracy (%) for each feature selection scheme (Scheme 1: Features selected using average values, statistical *t*-test and boxplots; Scheme 2: Features selected using feature importance score).

Scheme 1					Scheme 2				
Classifier	75%–25%	5-Fold	10-Fold	LOO	Classifier	75%–25%	5-Fold	10-Fold	LOO
LDA	87.83	87.70	87.75	70.36	LDA	87.97	87.78	87.83	72.27
DT	93.61	93.37	93.47	68.52	DT	94.36	93.76	94.31	69.13
LR	81.09	81.59	81.61	59.61	LR	85.53	85.00	84.65	61.59
ADA	90.95	91.15	91.02	68.89	ADA	92.55	92.13	92.27	66.61
GB	92.41	92.94	93.01	67.71	GB	94.15	94.12	94.09	68.58
RF	93.97	86.91	87.10	62.97	RF	95.71	87.83	87.78	63.74
QDA	83.04	82.81	82.85	69.30	ExTree	89.15	89.47	88.89	62.01
SVM	80.31	80.28	81.05	38.75					
KNN	82.51	84.24	84.14	48.39					
GNB	78.61	78.97	79.01	64.26					

Abbreviations: ADA, adaptive boosting; DT, decision tree; GB, gradient boosting; GNB, gaussian naive bayes; KNN, k-nearest neighbour; LDA, linear discriminant analysis; LOO, leave-one-out; LR, logistic regression; QDA, quadratic discriminant analysis; RF, random forests; SVM, support vector machine.

Both full dataset and extracted features were evaluated using a variety of classifiers with the classification accuracy exhibiting high values in the case of all the data and yielding minimal drop when using the optimised dataset. These results are promising and encouraging, allowing to collect data from a larger number of subjects, also replicating stress and fatigue conditions, using additional visual and audio stress induction techniques. The obtained dataset will be used to develop algorithms for classifying anomalies. Finally, the shared control mechanism relying on the classifier will be able to detect whenever an involuntary command is issued, taking preventive measures, by enabling the ROV to either ignore the command or take other corrective measures in real time.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest that could be perceived as prejudicing the impartiality of the research.

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